

PRESS RELEASE

27.02.2025

Citidem Project

CitiDem is an EU funded project supported by Grant Agreement n.101147423 from the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA) under the Citizens, Equality, Rights and Values Programme (CERV). The CitiDem project will run from June 2024 to June 2026. Its mission is to empower individuals, promote civic engagement, and restore trust in democracy and governance throughout Europe.

CitiDem aims at enhancing citizen engagement and participation through a two-fold approach. It focuses on building the capacity of civil society organizations to inform and engage citizens while equipping citizens with the tools and knowledge to actively participate in democratic processes. The project employs a structured plan of action based on four phases: enriching knowledge and capacity, organizing Citizen Assemblies (CAs) for deliberative actions, bridging the gap in policymaking, and ensuring the sustainability of CitiDem's results. By engaging various organizations across Europe and implementing activities in several EU countries, CitiDem strives to rebuild trust in democracy and governance, foster citizen participation, and prepare a European Citizen Initiative. The project targets citizens, civil society organizations, and policymakers, emphasizing both in-person and online activities to maximize participation and impact.

Over the next two years, **CitiDem will hold local citizen assemblies in eight EU countries** focusing on crucial topics.

- **Greece:** "Democracy vs. Disinformation in the Digital Era: Addressing disinformation and enhancing citizen participation online"
- **Italy:** "Climate crisis and Green New Deal"
- **Germany:** "Democracy Unboxed: Bridging EU-German Democracy in a Comparative Analysis: democracy, democratic instruments and citizens' participation"
- **France:** "Diversity and inclusivity in democracy: we can do better!"
- **Portugal:** "Public engagement on climate change and the green transition"
- **Slovenia:** "Political participation of all for the Europe of equals"
- **Austria:** "Labor, Migration & Climate Justice"
- **The Netherlands:** "Green transition and circular economy"

At the beginning as well as at the end of the CitiDem project, Transnational Citizens' Assemblies will be organized.

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Webinar "How to make citizens' assemblies resonate?"

ZOOM
17 February, 2025

Citizen participation is crucial for effective policymaking, ensuring that decisions reflect public needs, conditions, and preferences, and promoting accountability and transparency. CitiDem's strategic objective is to build the knowledge, tools, and support needed for citizens and civil society organizations to engage actively in democracy. The initiative aims to bridge the gap between policymakers and citizens, ensuring that every citizen has the means and know-how to participate in shaping the future of Europe.

Upcoming events:

The **University of Bologna** will host the first CitiDem event – **A webinar** titled **"How to Make Citizens' Assemblies Resonate?"**.

Scheduled for Monday, February 17th from 16:00 to 18:00 CET, this webinar will explore the effectiveness of citizens' assemblies in actively involving citizens amidst increasing distrust in democratic politics.

Three distinguished scholars with extensive expertise in citizens' assemblies:

- **Melisa Ross** (University of Bremen)
- **Andrea Felicetti** (University of Padova), and
- **Yves Sintomer** (University of Paris 8)—will join us to discuss how to ensure that assemblies engage citizens in a meaningful and empowering way.

The poster features the CitiDem logo at the top. The main title is "How to make citizens' assemblies resonate?". Below it, it says "Assemblies and effective citizen engagement". The event details are: "Webinar Monday 17 February 16.00-18.00 CET". The speakers listed are "With: Melisa Ross, Andrea Felicetti, Yves Sintomer". There are small portraits of the speakers. At the bottom, it says "Registration (Zoom): https://citizenstakeover.eu/citidem/" and "ALMA MATER STUDIORUM UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA". A URL at the very bottom reads "We want to know your views on citizen engagement! citizenstakeover.eu/citidem/#consultation".

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European Citizens' Assembly in Brussels

Université Libre de Bruxelles
7-8 March 2025

Eumans is organizing a Citizens' Assembly focused on democratic innovation and its role in affirming citizens' rights. This unique gathering, part of the CITIDEM Project's Transnational Citizens' Assembly on European Democracy Reform, will take place on March 7-8, 2025, at the Université Libre de Bruxelles.

This assembly aims to explore effective advocacy for citizens' rights through democratic innovation, beginning with the case of abortion rights as a catalyst for broader discussions.

Day 1 (March 7): Informative Session

- Expert presentations on direct action rights and deliberative democracy tools
- Insights from committees and associations on current proposals
- Opportunity to co-design a democratic innovation process

Day 2 (March 8): Deliberative Session

- Development of concrete recommendations for European democracy reform
- Exploration of innovative tools for citizen participation
- Crafting a blueprint for deliberative advocacy actions

If you're interested in being part of this transformative experience, please fill in the [participation form](#).

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Funded by
the European Union